

Figure S1. Side views of the reconstructed crystal structures of the complete 6-fold interpenetrated structures of Marta-COF-3 (top) and 4 (bottom).

Figure S2. FTIR Spectra of benzene-1,4-diboronic acid (grey), 3D-HBC (black) and Marta-COF-3 (blue).

Figure S3. FTIR Spectra of pyrene-2,7-diboronic acid (grey), 3D-HBC (black) and Marta-COF-4 (green).

Figure S4. Absorption spectra of Marta-COF-3 and 4.

Figure S5. SS¹³C NMR Spectrum of Marta-COF-3.

Figure S6. SS¹³C NMR Spectrum of Marta-COF-4.

Figure S7. SS^{11}B NMR Spectrum of Marta-COF-3.

Figure S8. SS^{11}B NMR Spectrum of Marta-COF-4.

Figure S9. Thermogravimetric analysis of Marta-COF-3 and Marta-COF-4 performed at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ under N_2 .

Figure S10. PXRD analysis for Marta-COF-3 including the experimental diffraction pattern (red line), Pawley refined pattern (blue line), and the difference between the refined and experimental pattern (pink line).

Figure S11. PXRD analysis for Marta-COF-4 including the experimental diffraction pattern (red line), Pawley refined pattern (blue line), and the difference between the refined and experimental pattern (green line).

Figure S12. Unit cells of Marta-COF-3 and 4 with increasing dihedral (twist) angles on the 3D-HBC nodes yielding different degrees of interpenetration, namely: three-fold, six-fold and nine-fold, for $\pm 1c$, $\pm 2c$ and $\pm 3c$ respectively. The $\pm c$ notation describes the unit cell connectivity in the c direction corresponding to the vertical direction on the page.

Figure S13. Comparison of the experimental and simulated PXRD patterns of Marta-COF-3 with increasing dihedral (twist) angles on the 3D-HBC nodes with different $\pm c$ (unit cell connectivity).

Figure S14. Comparison of the experimental and simulated PXRD patterns of Marta-COF-4 with increasing dihedral (twist) angles at the 3D-HBC nodes with different $\pm c$ (unit cell connectivity).

Figure S15. Optimized crystal structures and total energies of Marta-COF-3 (top) and Marta-COF-4 (bottom) 3x3x3 supercells starting from AA and "AB" arrangements at the TB level. Note that "AB" converges into a quasi-AA arrangement with essentially the same total energy.

Figure S16. High-resolution scanning electron microscopy images of Marta-COF-3 (a, b) and Marta-COF-4 (c, d) recorded using an in-lens SEM detector and the 1 keV electron beam and 50-100 pA current.

Figure S17. Large field of view SEM image of Marta-COF-3 using the 2 keV e-beam and a lateral secondary electrons detector (a); and Marta-COF-4 using an in-lens detector (b, c) and the 1 keV e-beam at 50 pA or 2 keV e-beam at 500 pA respectively. SEM image of an individual Marta-COF-4 particle with a top layer of COF removed, revealing 50-100 nm mesopores (d), and STEM image (20 keV e-beam at 500 pA) revealing triangular-shaped individual nanocrystallites (e).

Figure S18. HR TEM micrographs of Marta-COF-3.

Figure S19. HR TEM micrographs of Marta-COF-4.

Table S1. $\varphi\Sigma\mu_{\max}$ values observed on 2D COFs.

COF	$\varphi\Sigma\mu_{\max}$ (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Reference
COF-366	4.1×10^{-5}	[1]
COF-66	1.7×10^{-5}	[1]
NiPc COF	3.9×10^{-5}	[2]
CuPc COF	1.4×10^{-4}	[3]
ZnPc COF	2.2×10^{-4}	[3]
CoPc COF	2.6×10^{-4}	[3]
H ₂ P COF	1.8×10^{-4}	[4]
HPB COF	0.8×10^{-5}	[5]
HBC COF	1.5×10^{-5}	[5]
2D-NiPc-BTDA COF	5.8×10^{-4}	[6]
2D D-A COF	1.5×10^{-4}	[7]
Zn-Por-COF	3.0×10^{-5}	[8]
TTF-Ph-COF	1.1×10^{-5}	[9]
Marta-COF-1	0.6×10^{-4}	[10]

Experimental procedures

Reagents for synthesis were, if not otherwise specified, purchased from Aldrich, TCI or Acros Organics. Column chromatography was carried out using Silica gel 60 (40-60 μm) from Scharlab. Analytical thin layer chromatography (TLC) was done using aluminum sheets (20x20 cm) pre-coated with silica gel RP-18W 60 F254 from Merck. UV-active compounds were detected with a UV-lamp from CAMAG at wavelength $\lambda = 254$ or 366 nm. Pyrene-2,7-diboronic acid^[11] and 2,3,6,7,10,11,14,15,18,19,22,23-dodecamethoxy-*cata*-hexabenzocoronene^[12] were synthesized according to reported methods.

Marta-COF-3 and Marta-COF-4 were synthesized in pre-scored 5 mL ampoules from Aldrich. For their synthesis and purification anhydrous solvents were used. Anhydrous acetone (99.8%) was purchased from Acros Organics. THF was dried using an Innovative Pure Solve solvent purification system and mesitylene (97%) and DMA (99+%) were obtained from Acros Organics and dried with molecular sieves.

NMR spectra in solution were recorded on Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer at room temperature using partially deuterated solvents as internal standards. Coupling constants (J) are denoted in Hz and chemical shifts (δ) in ppm. Multiplicities are denoted as follows: s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, br = broad.

Solid-State ^1H , ^{11}B and ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 400 MHz NMR spectrometer at a MAS rate of 10 kHz and a CP contact time of 2 ms.

Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization (coupled to a Time-Of-Flight analyzer) experiments (MALDI-TOF) were recorded on Bruker REFLEX spectrometer in POLYMAT.

ATR-FTIR spectra were recorded on a Bruker ALPHA ATR-IR spectrometer. Mettler Toledo TGA /SDTA 851 was used to perform the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a 10 $^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating rate under a nitrogen flow, which was changed to oxygen from 800 $^\circ\text{C}$. Previously to the scan, the samples were heated at 100 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 min under a nitrogen flow.

Powder electronic absorption spectra were recorded on a PerkinElmer Lambda 950 UV/VIS/NIR spectrophotometer.

Elemental analysis of the as-synthesized COFs was carried out in a Euro EA Elemental Analyzer from EuroVector.

The powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) measurements were collected by using a PHILIPS X'PERT PRO automatic diffractometer operating at 40 kV and 40 mA, in theta-theta configuration, secondary monochromator with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) and a PIXcel solid state detector (active length in 2θ 3.347 $^\circ$). Data were collected from 1 to 50 $^\circ$ 2θ (step size = 0.026 and time per step = 300 s,

total time 40 min) at room temperature. A variable divergence slit, giving a constant 4.0 mm area of sample illumination, was used.

The pore structure was evaluated by nitrogen sorption isotherms, measured at 77 K with a Micromeritics 3Flex apparatus. The samples were degassed in an Autosorb station at and 10^{-6} Torr at 100 °C prior to analysis. Surface areas, pore sizes and volume values were calculated from nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms (77 K). Specific surface area (SA) was calculated by multi-point Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method. Total pore volume was taken at $P/P_0=0.96$. Pore size distributions were analyzed by using the solid density functional theory (NLDFT) for the adsorption branch by assuming a cylindrical pore model.

Scanning Electron Microscopy. Powders of COF materials were deposited onto SEM stubs or lacey-carbon coated Cu TEM grids, and imaged in their native form, without additional coating with metal or carbon. High-resolution SEM images have been recorded on ZEISS Crossbeam 550 FIB-SEM system using e-beam of different energies and different currents, and either an in-lens or a lateral secondary electron detectors, or an STEM detector (as specified in figure captions).

Electron Microscopy. All samples were prepared by dispersion in acetone and drop cast onto lacey carbon-coated copper TEM grids (Agar). High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM) analysis was performed on a JEOL2100F operating at 200 kV. The morphology of the samples was determined by taking low magnification (ca. x 30k mag) images from different regions of the specimen, and the nanoscale features were imaged using high resolution imaging (ca. x 100k mag).

FP-TRMC experiments were conducted for the sample on a quartz plate using the third harmonic generator (THG; 355 nm) of a Nd:YAG laser (Continuum Inc., Surelite II, 5–8 ns pulse duration, 10 Hz) as the excitation source (9.1×10^{15} photons cm^{-2} pulse $^{-1}$). The frequency and power of microwave were ~9.1 GHz and 3 mW, respectively. The photoconductivity transient $\Delta\sigma$ was converted to the product of the quantum yield (ϕ) and the sum of charge carrier mobilities $\Sigma\mu$ ($= \mu_+ + \mu_-$) by the formula $\phi\Sigma\mu = \Delta\sigma(eI_0F_{\text{light}})^{-1}$, where e and F_{light} are the unit charge of a single electron and a correction (or filling) factor, respectively.

Synthesis and characterization

3D-HBC: 2,3,6,7,10,11,14,15,18,19,22,23-dodecamethoxy-cata-hexabenzocoronene (50 mg, 0.052 mmol) was dissolved in dichloromethane (2.5 mL) and then BBr₃ (1M solution in dichloromethane) was added (2.5 mL) at 0 °C. The suspension was stirred overnight at room temperature. Then, the solvents were removed with a nitrogen flow and water was added (8 mL). The solid was filtered quickly and washed with water. Finally, the solid was dried under vacuum (quantitative yield).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 9.74 (s, 12H), 8.53 (s, 12H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 145.52, 123.86, 122.07, 118.36, 112.23. EM (MALDI-TOF) (m/z): calculated for C₄₈H₂₄O₁₂: 792.127; found: 792.120 [M]⁺.

Marta-COF-3: 3D-HBC (12.10 mg, 0.015 mmol) and benzene-1,4-diboronic acid (7.59 mg, 0.046 mmol) were sonicated in 1.8 mL of a mixture of degassed dimethylacetamide/mesitylene (1:1) in a pre-scored 5 mL ampoule under nitrogen. The suspension was degassed by using three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. The ampoule was sealed off using flame and heated at 140 °C for 7 days. The powder was collected by filtration and washed five times with anhydrous tetrahydrofurane and acetone, affording a green powder that was dried at 30 °C under vacuum for 24 hours (15 mg, 93% yield).

SS¹H NMR (δ) (ppm): 7.85. SS¹³C NMR (δ) (ppm): 145.0, 133.9, 123.2, 109.3. ATR-FTIR (cm⁻¹): 1524, 1466, 1346, 1229, 1154, 1078, 1021. Elemental Analysis: calculated C (73.83%), H (2.25%), B (6.04%), O (17.88%); observed C (69.01%), H (4.28%). It has been noted^[13] that elemental analysis of boronate COFs is not very accurate because of the formation of refractory non-combustible boron carbide byproducts.

Marta-COF-4: 3D-HBC (14.29 mg, 0.018 mmol) and pyrene-2,7-diboronic acid (15.66 mg, 0.054 mmol) were sonicated in 2 mL of a mixture of degassed dimethylacetamide/mesitylene (1:1) in a pre-scored 5 mL ampoule under nitrogen. The suspension was degassed by using three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. The ampoule was sealed off using flame and heated at 140 °C for 7 days. The green precipitate was collected by filtration and washed five times with anhydrous tetrahydrofurane and acetone. The powder was dried at 30 °C under vacuum for 24 hours. 24 mg of Marta-3DCOF-Py was obtained (92% yield).

SS¹H NMR (δ) (ppm): 7.85. SS¹³C NMR (δ) (ppm): 145.2, 128.9, 122.7, 109.2. ATR-FTIR (cm⁻¹): 1459, 1348, 1234, 1155, 899. Elemental Analysis: calculated C (79.73%), H (2.51%), B (4.48%), O (13.28%); observed C (62.65%), H (4.22%). It has been noted^[13] that elemental analysis of boronate COFs is not very accurate because of the formation of refractory non-combustible boron carbide byproducts.

NMR spectra of 3D-HBC

Figure S20. ^1H NMR spectrum of 3D-HBC (400 MHz, DMSO-d_6 , 298 K).

Figure S21. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 3D-HBC (100 MHz, DMSO-d_6 , 298 K).

Computer models

Tight Binding (TB) calculations were fundamental to explore different interlayer stackings and crystalline cells. For this, the Matsci parameter augmented with dispersion attractive corrections from the OPLSAA force-field^[14] as implemented into the DFTB+ software was used.^[15]

Final calculations for the minimal unit cell were computed with DFT with the Fritz Haber Institute ab initio molecular simulations (FHI-aims) package^[16] using “light” numeric atomic orbitals, which approximately correspond to TZVP level of calculations with Gaussian type orbitals. The PBE functional augmented with Many Body Dispersion corrections (MBD^[17]) was used for full geometry optimizations and binding energies.

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